

SZ-HB-II-01-02 Planing an exchange semester (English)

Author	@Julia Lehmler ; @ Ricarda Peil ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Alexander Schröter ; @ Sönke Erdmann ; @Julia Victoria Dinier (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091353
ID	SZ-HB-II-01-02
Title	Planing an exchange semester
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P. Kaja - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286
Short description	Kaja is planning a semester abroad in France and is collecting the necessary documents at work.
Result	Kaja stores relevant information about the semester abroad clearly and easily accessible in her workspace.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Information gathering for an exchange semester"• Part 2: "Create your own workspace: Exchange semester in France"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Kaja is registered at BIRD• Kaja is logged in to BIRD
Components	#chat #workspace #learningpathfinder
Services / tools	#video-conference

Problem scenario

Introduction

Kaja Stanke is planning a semester abroad in France as part of her bachelor's degree. So far, Kaja hasn't gathered much information about how the semester will run and what will be needed. However, being well-organized is crucial for Kaja.

Problem definition

Kaja attaches great importance to the semester abroad and therefore wants to prepare well for it. Kaja sees the semester abroad as an opportunity for personal and academic experience, as well as an important part of her resume. To be well prepared and plan

everything successfully, Kaja needs various information and forms. Tips or best practice examples are also helpful to ensure that nothing important is forgotten.

Background and context

It has always been Kaja's dream to spend a semester abroad during her studies. Kaja knows that you have to apply and go through an official process. Kaja wants to approach this process as structured as possible and avoid unnecessary paperwork.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Kaja has a strong need for security and organization, which can make the uncertainty of planning her semester abroad stressful and hectic. Therefore, it's important that all preparatory tasks are completed in advance so that she can fully concentrate on her application afterwards.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Kaja received basic information about the semester abroad from the university's Erasmus advisor. However, they always has little time for consultations. Kaja's schedule is also very full, making it difficult to visit the institute during office hours. Searching online yields too much disparate information for Kaja. Kaja wants to have all the relevant information for they Erasmus exchange in France, as well as useful information about France and French universities, clearly arranged and readily available in one place.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Information gathering for an exchange semester"

Step 1: Kaja creates a project in her own workspace and calls it "Erasmus-Planing".

Step 2: Kaja first creates a rough schedule to structure her own planning.

Step 3: First, Kaja creates different folders in the "Erasmus Planning" workspace to organize the links, notes, and possible processes herself or store them separately. The folders are named "Useful Links," "References," "Notes," and "Application."

Step 4: The "Texteditor" is opened in the "Term Paper" folder so that planning can be carried directly in the workspace and manage the selected notes and links such as the [ERASMUS - checklist](#).

Step 5: Now Kaja opens the LearningPathFinder and searches for information about an exchange semester.

Step 6: The LearningPathFinder shows various links ([Studying and living in France - DAAD](#); [exchange semester in France - study worldwide](#); [Erasmus+ in France | Campus France](#)), Checklists and materials on this topic. These also include testimonials and tips

from students.

Step 7: Kaja selects individual links (these contain short descriptions, so that it is clear what each link is about) and saves the most important ones as bookmarks.

Step 8: Kaja saves the links she has already collected in the "Useful Links" folder, so that she can access them again and again during her search.

Step 9: Kaja repeatedly opens and closes the workspace, adds documents, and updates the information. Every time BIRD is opened again, Kaja gets a quick overview of what has already been done.

Part 2: "Create your own workspace: Exchange semester in France"

Step 1: Kaja opens the folder "Erasmus Application" in the project "Erasmus-Planning" and applies online for an Erasmus stay in France for the following academic year via the [Mobilitätsportal](#), [Mobility-Online Portal](#).

Step 2: Kaja receives an acceptance from Erasmus and now makes an appointment with the coordinator to discuss which universities in France are suitable and which courses from France can be credited to her home university.

Step 3: In her own workspace, Kaja creates the folder "Erasmus exchange semester" and transfer all new information, links and correspondence with the Erasmus coordinator there.

Step 4: Because Kaja wants to have the credits earned in France recognized to the home university, the links and documents (applications) researched for this purpose are also saved directly in the "Preparation for a exchange semester" folder, so they can be accessed immediately after the semester ends.